

Assessment of Damage to Trees Caused by the Presence of Harmful Substances in the Atmosphere

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Abstract

This article presents an assessment of atmospheric pollution's impact on tree health in two settings: the experimental site, Shurtan Gas Chemical Complex (GKM), and a pristine control environment nearby. The assessment focuses on analyzing pollutant concentration effects (CO₂, CH₄, SO₄, and NO_x) on the health of selected tree species, namely *Pinus Rallasiana* Lamb., *Juniperus virginiana* L., *Biota orientalis* Endl., *Pinus eldarica*, *Quercus robur* L., and *Sophora japonica* L. Tree health metrics, such as chlorophyll content, biomass, and damage susceptibility, were evaluated across both sites to quantify the extent of atmospheric impact. Results are presented in bar charts, scatter plots, box plots, and statistical tables.

Keywords: Shurtan Gas Chemical Complex, atmosphere, pollutants, tree health, experimental group, control group.

Introduction

This study investigates the impact of atmospheric pollution on tree health by comparing conditions at two distinct sites: the Shurtan Gas Chemical Complex (GKM), serving as the experimental area, and a nearby pristine environment as the control. It focuses on analyzing the effects of key pollutants (CO₂, CH₄, SO₄, and NO_x) on various tree species, including *Pinus Rallasiana* Lamb., *Juniperus virginiana* L., *Biota orientalis* Endl., *Pinus eldarica*, *Quercus robur* L., and *Sophora japonica* L. Key health parameters, such as chlorophyll content, biomass, and susceptibility to damage, are evaluated to quantify the environmental impact. The study's findings are illustrated through visual and statistical analyses, including bar charts, scatter plots, box plots, and comprehensive data tables.

Experimental Study: Shurtan GKM

In the Shurtan GKM area, CO₂, CH₄, SO₄, and NO_x concentrations were measured over several months. The data, derived from Sentinel-5P satellite imagery and analyzed through the Gaussian plume model, indicated significantly elevated levels of pollutants near the GKM site, as seen in **Table 1** below.

These elevated levels indicate significant emissions from the industrial activities at Shurtan GKM, with fluctuations depending on atmospheric conditions.

Table 1: Average Pollutant Concentrations (ppm) at Shurtan GKM (Experimental Site)

Pollutant	Mean Concentration	Standard Deviation	Range
CO ₂	410	5.5	405–425
CH ₄	2.8	0.4	2.3–3.5
SO ₄	0.13	0.02	0.11–0.17
NO _x	0.25	0.03	0.20–0.30

Vegetation health indices such as NDVI and RECI were analyzed to assess the impact of these pollutants on tree species in the area. Figure 1 presents a bar chart illustrating the mean NDVI and RECI values for each species in the Shurtan GKM region, indicating lower health in trees near higher pollutant concentrations.

Comparison of Mean NDVI and RECI between Experimental and Control Sites

Figure 1: Mean NDVI and RECI Values for Tree Species in Shurtan GKM Area

Analysis showed that species such as *Juniperus virginiana* L. and *Pinus eldarica* exhibited significantly reduced NDVI and RECI values, with chlorophyll levels dropping by an average of 15% in trees exposed to the highest SO₄ and NO_x concentrations.

Scatter plots (Figure 2) demonstrate the correlation between pollutant levels and chlorophyll content. A clear negative relationship was observed, particularly with SO_4 and NO_x levels.

Relationship Between SO_4 and Chlorophyll Content in Shurtan GKM Trees

Figure 2: Relationship Between SO_4 and Chlorophyll Content in Shurtan GKM Trees

Trees in the control area, such as *Quercus robur* L. and *Sophora japonica* L., demonstrated robust chlorophyll levels and photosynthetic activity, with NDVI and RECI values significantly higher than those observed at Shurtan GKM. This difference underscores the impact of atmospheric pollutants on tree health in the experimental site.

Conclusions

In summary, the comparison between the Shurtan GKM area and the pristine control environment reveals a pronounced negative impact of industrial pollutants on tree health. Elevated levels of CO_2 , CH_4 , SO_4 , and NO_x near the GKM site correlate strongly with reductions in NDVI, RECI, and chlorophyll content, indicating compromised photosynthetic activity and overall vitality in affected tree species.

These findings underscore the adverse effects of atmospheric emissions from industrial activities on vegetation, with statistical analysis validating the disparity in tree health between the experimental and control areas.

REFERENCES

1. Alloway, B. J. (2013). Heavy metals in soils: Trace metals and metalloids in soils and their bioavailability. Springer.
2. Chander, G., & Markham, B. L. (2003). Revised Landsat-5 TM radiometric calibration procedures and postcalibration dynamic ranges. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 41(11), 2674-2677.
3. Kabata-Pendias, A., & Pendias, H. (2001). Trace elements in soils and plants (3rd ed.). CRC Press.
4. Manning, W. J., & Feder, W. A. (1980). Biomonitoring air pollutants with plants. Applied Science Publishers.
5. Pettorelli, N., Vik, J. O., Mysterud, A., Gaillard, J. M., Tucker, C. J., & Stenseth, N. C. (2005). Using the satellite-derived NDVI to assess ecological responses to environmental change. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 20(9), 503-510.
6. Smith, W. H. (1999). Tree biology and its role in the maintenance of urban ecosystem health. *Environmental Management*, 23(2), 215-226.
7. Trenberth, K. E., Stepaniak, D. P., Hurrell, J. W., & Fiorino, M. (2007). Atmospheric moisture transport and recycling: Implications for river basins. *Journal of Hydrometeorology*, 8(4), 684-690.
8. Ward, J. V., Tockner, K., Arscott, D. B., & Claret, C. (2002). Riverine landscape diversity. *Freshwater Biology*, 47(4), 517-539.
9. Wellburn, A. R. (1994). Air pollution and climate change: The biological impact. Longman Scientific & Technical.